

1.11w agreed with the reported⁶ values of CeO_2 . The specific surface area values (m^2g^{-1}) 7.2 (ceria-I), 7.4 (ceria-II) and 7.3 (ceria-III), are also the same within the experimental error and are very low. The products of decomposition of alcohols over ceria are found to be olefines and ketones as obtained in the dehydration and dehydrogenation respectively. Thus, cyclohexanol gives a mixture of cyclohexene and cyclohexanone and menthol decomposes to menthenes and menthone. 3-Methyl-2-pentanol on dehydration gives a mixture of isomers namely 3-methyl-1-pentene and 3-methyl-2-pentene (*cis* and *trans*) whereas 4-methyl-2-pentanol dehydrates to give 4-methyl-1-pentene and 4-methyl-2-pentene (*cis* and *trans*). These two alcohols on dehydrogenation afforded methylpentanones. The tertiary alcohol 3-methyl-3-pentanol, was found to undergo only dehydration to give 3-methyl-2-pentene. The results of the analyses of the corresponding olefines and ketones, the products of alcohol decomposition over thoria, are given in Table 1. The results suggest that the three ceria

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Dielectric Polarisation of Alkylquinolines and Molecular Interaction in Solution

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Manuscript received 19 February 1980, revised 13 October 1980,
accepted 28 January 1981

TABLE 1—DECOMPOSITION OF ALCOHOLS OVER CERIA

Alcohol	Catalyst	Conversion %	Product Dehydration olefines*	Distribution (%) Dehydrogenation ketones**
Menthol	Ceria-I	39	33	67
	Ceria-II	40	29	71
	Ceria-III	35	29	71
3-Methyl-2-pentanol	Ceria-I	90	25	75
	Ceria-II	75	30	70
	Ceria-III	70	35	65
4-Methyl-2-pentanol	Ceria-I	15	36	64
	Ceria-II	17	40	60
	Ceria-III	14	36	64
3-Methyl-3-pentanol	Ceria-I	88	100	—
	Ceria-II	86	100	—
	Ceria-III	86	100	—

Catalyst weight: 5 gms; Flow-rate: 12 ml hr⁻¹; Temp.: 360-375°

* Olefines obtainable from the different alcohols have been enumerated in the text.

**The ketone obtainable from the different alcohols have also been listed out in the text.

samples behave more or less similarly towards a particular alcohol. The per cent conversion under the conditions of the experiment is minimum for 4-methyl-2-pentanol and is maximum for 3-methyl-3-pentanol. Excepting in the case of the tertiary alcohol, 3-methyl-3-pentanol, other three alcohols undergo both dehydration and dehydrogenation, the latter being twice as that of the former process.

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A survey of literature¹ reveals that in past dielectric measurements have been carried out only on 2-methyl quinoline in benzene. Consequently our attention was drawn to carry out such measurements on other alkyl quinolines in non-polar solvents. The primary object of the present investigation was to study the interaction between solute and solvent involving the π -electron system of the solutes reported earlier².

Experimental

The method and technique have been described elsewhere^{3,4}.

Results and Discussion

The variation of moments in solution have been discussed in the light of Higasi's theory^{5,6,7} using the data of tensor ellipsoid for quinoline along three principal axes as $b_1 = 1.64$, $b_2 = 2.29$ and $b_3 = 0.75$.

Fig. 1. Direction of Tensor Ellipsoids.

The theory suggests that the ratio of semiaxes c and a for quinoline very with tensor ellipsoid values

as follows :

$$\frac{c}{a} = \frac{2.29}{1.64} = 1.40$$

Since $\frac{c}{a}$ is greater than unity, the theory predicts a positive solvent effect in case of quinoline. On the introduction of methyl group either in position 2 or 6 the molecules get elongated and hence the value of b_2 increases further. Eventually $\frac{c}{a}$ becomes further greater than unity. Consequently a positive solvent affect is expected in such cases. Unfortunately moment values for these compounds in vapour state are not available, hence a direct comparison is not possible. However, the theory reports that greater would be apparent moment values in a solvent having higher dielectric constant. Evidently the obtained data in Table 1 show that the apparent moment μ_s in benzene in all cases are greater than those in cyclohexane. This order has been reported⁸ on the basis of microwave measurements. This can be further justified from pK_a values which measures the availability of electrons for polarisation.

TABLE 1—APPARENT DIPOLE MOMENT IN SOLUTION (μ_s)

Solvent	Solute		
	2-methyl quinoline $pK_a=5.42$	6-methyl quinoline $pK_a=4.92$	8-methyl quinoline $pK_a=4.60$
Benzene	1.89	2.25	1.51
Carbon tetrachloride	2.19	2.30	1.75
Dioxane	1.90	1.87	1.32
Cyclohexane	1.87	2.14	1.43

Since the pK_a of 6-methyl quinoline is greater than that for 8-methyl quinoline, the apparent moment is expected in this order. Contrary to the expectation the moment value of 2-methyl quinoline is lower than that of 6-methyl quinoline. This anomaly may be due to the steric nature of methyl group dominant in ortho position. Evidences are available in literature⁹ in favour of this suggestion. Further the smaller values for 2 and 8-methyl quinolines may be attributed to partial shielding of the hetero-nitrogen atom by methyl group with its attendants reducing intermolecular attraction. The higher values in carbon tetrachloride and apparent anomalies in dioxane are seemingly the result of specific interaction in these solvents. The nature of this interaction has already been studied by one of the authors^{3,4} in the light of Earp and Glasstone theory¹⁰. Accordingly, we observe that in all the

solvents the curves obtained by plotting $\left[\frac{\epsilon_{12}-1}{\epsilon_{12}+2}\right]^2$ vs P_{12} are linear and hence show the absence of chemical interaction in solution. Further the positive value of P^E (the excess polarisation) submitted

in Table 2 eliminates the possibility of dipole association as well.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF EXCESS POLARISATION P^E WITH $f_1 f_2$

$f_1 f_2$	0.01041	0.02085	0.02965	0.03779	0.04766	0.05348	0.06197
P^E	+0.435	+0.766	+1.202	+1.547	+1.950	+2.376	+2.626
(6-methyl quinoline+carbon tetrachloride)							
$f_1 f_2$	0.00189	0.00569	0.00923	0.01239	0.01571	0.01855	
P^E	+0.157	+0.348	+0.534	+0.680	+0.833	+1.044	
(8-methyl quinoline+carbon tetrachloride)							
$f_1 f_2$	0.00280	0.00643	0.00909	0.01240	0.01572	0.01787	
P^E	-0.009	+0.053	+0.125	+0.180	+0.220	+0.313	

f_1 = mole fraction of the solvent ;
 f_2 = mole fraction of the solute.

However the variation of P^E with $f_1 f_2$ (Fig.2) for the systems,

2-methyl quinoline+carbon tetrachloride
8-methyl quinoline+carbon tetrachloride

Fig. 2. Excess polarisation vs $f_1 f_2$ in carbontetrachloride.

show a linear relation and the curves pass through the origin. This suggests the formation of charge transfer complexes in carbon tetrachloride. The specific interaction accordingly to Goats, Sullivan and Ott¹¹ appear to be of the donor acceptor type. For 2 and 8-methyl quinolines, it is expected that the nitrogen atom of methyl quinolines donate π -electrons to the empty 3d level of the chlorine atom in carbon tetrachloride. This view is supported by Mullikan¹² and Baliah¹³. Surprisingly 6-methyl quinoline does not indicate such interactions in carbon tetrachloride. This may be explained in terms of $\Delta\mu$ values (Table 3) which measures the extent of interaction in carbon tetrachloride,

TABLE 3—INCREMENT OF APPARENT MOMENT IN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE

Solute	μ_s (Benzene) (1)	μ_s (Carbon tetrachloride)	$\Delta\mu$ [[2] - (1)]
2-methyl quinoline	1.89	2.19	+0.30
6-methyl quinoline	2.25	2.30	+0.05
8-methyl quinoline	1.51	1.75	+0.24

The apparent inability of dielectric measurement in detecting a weak interaction corresponding to $\Delta\mu=0.05$ also assist in understanding the limitation of Earp and Glasstone theory.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. R. C. Kapoor for providing the necessary facilities and also to U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding fellowships to (A.K.M.) and (S.K.G.).

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Synthesis of Phenacyl Dithiocarbamates and 2-Thio- Δ^4 -Thiazolines

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Manuscript received 9 March 1979, revised 20 November 1980,
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THIOCARBAMATES¹, dithiocarbamates²⁻⁶ and thiocarbamoyl aryldisulphides^{7,8} possess pesticidal characteristics. The preparation of phenacyl dithiocarbamates was, therefore, undertaken.

Ammonium, alkylammonium and dialkylammonium dithiocarbamates react with phenacyl bromide exothermically to give phenacyl dithiocarbamates, which, however, cyclize to 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines, in the case of dithiocarbamates derived from primary amines. 2-Thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines⁹ too, are expected to be biologically active. Sahu *et al.*⁹ reported the synthesis of two such thiazolines. The infrared spectrum (KBr Pellet) of phenacyl dithiocarbamates shows carbonyl absorption around 1690 cm^{-1} , which is absent in that of 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines.

Preparation of Phenacyl dithiocarbamates and 2-Thio- Δ^4 -Thiazolines :

Ethanollic solutions of a dithiocarbamate (0.02 mole, ammonium dithiocarbamate¹⁰ derived from an aromatic amine, alkylammonium/dialkylammonium dithiocarbamate derived from an aliphatic amine prepared by reacting the aliphatic amine with carbondisulphide in ethanollic solution) and phenacyl bromide (0.02 mole) are mixed and kept at room temperature for 4 hours. The product which crystallizes on chilling is collected by suction filtration and washed with water. Recrystallization from ethanol affords pure compounds. Melting points and yields are recorded in Table 1. All the compounds exhibited analytical data consistent with their molecular composition.

TABLE 1—PHENACYL DITHIOCARBAMATES AND 2-THIO- Δ^4 -THIAZOLINES DERIVED FROM VARIOUS AMINES

Amine	m.p. ¹ of dithiocarbamate/ thio-thiazoline	% Yield
1. Morpholine	134	85
2. Piperidine	120	85
3. Di-isopropyl	66	50
4. N-Methylaniline	154	70
5. Aniline ²	133	80
6. p-Chloroaniline ³	123	70
7. o-Toluidine	97	75
8. p-Toluidine	109-11	80
9. m-Toluidine	137	70
10. p-Anisidine	85	70
11. p-Phenetidine	198	70
12. n-Propyl	100	65
13. n-Butyl	80	60
14. mono Ethanol	85	50

(1) Melting points are uncorrected, compounds 1 to 4 are phenacyl dithiocarbamates and the rest are 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines.

(2) Reported by B. Sahu, *et al.*

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M.M. Bokadia for providing research facilities and to C.S.I.R. for the award of a fellowship to (A. B.).

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